

Moonlighting and Employee Productivity

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ABSTRACT

The global economy & ecosystem are undergoing rapid transformations. In this era of economic upheaval, workers are more concerned with their personal financial security than with their career advancement. Because of this, they now have a second position with a separate business that pays better than their first. We might as well call what we have here employee moonlighting. Moonlighting has a variety of implications on an employee's work life as well as the employers' compliance policies. This study has led to comprehending few questions that arise from this activity of moonlighting, such as, is it proper that the individual works for two or more companies while keeping their current employer in the dark about it? How can businesses advise staff to support themselves financially so they don't engage in moonlighting? What if the employee is performing each task more effectively than before without interfering with any of them? As employee moonlighting activities transition from blue moon to full moon, all of these issues are very concerning.

Keywords: Moonlighting, Blue moonlighting, Full moonlighting, Quarter moonlighting, Half moonlighting, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, "moonlighting" has been used to refer to taking on additional, unrelated labor in addition to one's primary occupation. One possible example is someone who works as an instructor throughout day and runs a tutoring business in evening. While many people take on extra labor to make ends meet, others do so to learn more about their chosen field or simply to keep themselves from going stir crazy at home. There are many reasons why people take on extra work, but whatever the case, it can wear them down.

If workers aren't satisfied with their existing compensation packages, they might start working extra hours to make ends meet. There is resentment among workers who believe their employers are taking advantage of them in order to increase earnings. All facets of human resource management are likely to be affected by employees' extra work. Staffing agencies face challenges when employees freelance, as this behavior may have a significant impact on productivity.

➤ Reasons of moonlighting-

Today, the majority of employed individuals seek side jobs for:

- Extra money: To earn extra money from what they are getting currently from one job, to save or to satisfy some needs.
- Exhibiting their abilities in various work profiles: multi-talented employees prefer to keep their skills sharpened and optimized, which leads to their indulgence in different job roles of interest.
- Non-recognition by employer: When employees don't feel appreciated for their efforts, it leads them to looking for alternatives where they are treated considerably.
- making use of leisure time: Some employees have multiple interests and prefer to use their leisure to engage in those interests rather than sitting idle.

➤ Types of Moonlighting Practices

Four criteria can be used to categorize moonlighting:

1. Blue Moonlighting

After receiving negative feedback about their performance, some workers may decide to work a second employment to make ends meet. They are not able to secure a second job because of their shortage of skills. The futility of such an effort is often referred to as "blue moonlighting."

2. Quarter Moonlighting

Employees who aren't happy with their compensation may seek out "quarter moonlighting," or a second position to work alongside to their regular one.

3. Half Moonlighting

Some employees have a propensity for living above their means. In light of this, they split their time evenly between their full-time employment and a second part-time business. Sometimes referred to as "half mooning," this is a hybrid of working full and part time.

4. Full Moonlighting

Some workers establish startups while also contributing part-time to their regular workplaces. This can happen if an employee realizes they've got a lot of free time at work or if they believe their salary is inadequate compared to what they and their peers have made. Such workers engage in full moonlighting when their subsequent employment becomes so important that it affects every aspect of their lives, including their social standing.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- Understanding notion of moonlighting.
- Understanding effect of moonlighting on employee efficiency.
- Understanding effect of moonlighting on the organization.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Semion and Adebisi (2019) It has been found that professionals and managers working in the public sector moonlight more often. Moonlighting, according to his findings, leads to a disloyal & unhappy workforce, increases complexity, promotes a carefree attitude towards work, fosters ineffective leadership, and undermines the effectiveness of organizations. He also proposed that government establish suitable measures to outlaw moonlighting by state employees.

Sabron & Hassim (2018) drew the conclusion that a lot of public servants have side jobs. They surveyed hospital workers to gauge their opinions on public sector moonlighting practices. The research set out to determine what factors in the workplace, on the part of workers, influence their decision to take on side gigs. Finding that workers' involvement in moonlighting was positively correlated with personal and external variables, the study concluded that it's challenging & time-consuming for managers to adopt moonlighting in a company. It's clear from the results that both internal and external variables play a role in whether or not workers decide to take on extra work. It is suggested that government provide opportunities for employees to gain managerial experience through part-time employment.

Ara and Akbar (2016) pointed out how part-time work affects happiness of professors at Pakistan's state universities. They found that four factors—the desire for professional development, the inability to advance in one's current position, desire for greater independence in one's work, and the desire for financial gain—drive moonlighting amongst university faculty. They emphasized that working a second job has a big impact on job happiness.

Ashwini et al investigated the motivations for side work in the IT industry. the individual who worked a second job, whether for financial or other reasons. They discovered that people work second jobs to take care of their economic issues or increased financial responsibilities in their household to meet non-financial interests. Employees' secondary work is something they undertake in their spare time and not just for pay. Total hours worked in side occupations, as well as financial and non-financial motivations, may be used to determine the types and extent of moonlighting. They found that there numerous aspects which can influence an employee's decision to hold several jobs, with family size being the main one. According to the survey, employees who were married or single had

different intentions about side jobs. An essential factor that contributed to the decision to moonlight is work experience. The reasons people moonlight also depend on demographic variables.

Shweta (2014) examined the various facets of employees' side jobs. She discussed the need to comprehend why employees moonlight while analyzing numerous concerns relating to it. She made suggestions on how to stop moonlighting for businesses and workers.

Betts (2011) The gender inequalities among instructors who work extra shifts have been researched. He discovered that the patterns of behavior for professors who moonlight differ between men and women. There were disparities in income, type, and frequency of moonlighting activities.

Gayatri, it has been shown that employees who moonlight tend to have higher standards of life, and they frequently try out other jobs to see how their talents fare. Job happiness and money rewards can discourage moonlighting. She learned the repercussions of having a second employment on the part of both the boss and the employee. There could be an inconsistency between the emotional and bodily obligations placed on an employee as an outcome of their side gig. Staff members may also pursue entrepreneurial pursuits, such as starting a side company or working a second job, as a means of enhancing their employability. Employers can incentivize workers and reduce the prevalence of side gigs by providing both monetary and non-monetary benefits.. Employees can prevent moonlighting by taking advantage of employer job stability and work rotation.

Georgios et al (2011) Investigations into dynamics of human capital, having two jobs, & choosing amongst primary & secondary occupations were made. Additionally, influences & drivers of secondary employment were examined. He also looked into how doing numerous jobs affected one's primary job. According to their research, carrying two jobs simultaneously may also result in self-employment and new primary occupations.

Liyanapathirana et al (2021) According to this study, moonlighting was highly noted among two groups i.e. professionals and agricultural workers in Sri Lanka, its main rationale was to identify factors that influence involvement in moonlighting. The main problems faced farmers in three specific crops which include paddy, vegetables and tea. The agricultural sector in Sri Lanka has faced many challenges to increase productivity and reduce underemployment. Agricultural workers are one of the main reasons for moonlighting in Sri Lanka

Dr. A. Shaji George et al (2022) In accordance with this study, it was observed that there were rapid changes in the global environment and economy and the results were directly reflected for side jobs or moonlighting, some workers began to praise earning a living or basic needs. Many employees, especially during an economic transitional period, prioritize financial security over professional development.. There are several ways to think about duress, i.e. if an employee accepts a job offer outside the primary employer that is consistent with their ability to perform duties that may be subject to discipline.

As per research by **Sharon Brown et al**, In order to make ends meet, many instructors in the area have taken jobs outside of education. (Yavuz, 2009). Regardless of one's class size, instructor standards, level of rank, or the sort of school in which one works, a teacher's financial stress and physical and mental fatigue will have an adverse effect on student learning. (Yavuz, 2009). Santavirta (2007) discovered that many instructors experienced exhaustion because of high levels of tension they experienced on job. Fifty percent of students polled thought working part-time didn't hurt their grades.

Kamal Adetunji Bakare et al (2021) In this study, we examine the prevalence of part-time employment at state colleges in Nigeria. Their intention was to demonstrate that corporate culture is more compassionate, broad, and at times apathetic toward the methods of winking, remaining quiet, rules which condemn numerous job retentions, or transforming the tide by enforcing repressive regulations than that of our public universities. Inaction on this issue has been observed to have negative effects on practice and to be open to misunderstanding. Through their investigation, they were able to provide actual evidence linking numerous jobs to economic discontent by drawing on relative scarcity (RD) as well as social exchange theory. (SET). In conclusion, they claimed that proper policies must be devised to offset conventional practices in order to guarantee future security in workplace relations.

Fapohunda, Tinuke M. et al (2020) University professors in South West Nigeria were surveyed about their instruction, project management, and scholarly output. Three hundred forty-seven professors from two private and four state institutions in Nigeria's South West Zone were surveyed. All respondents were associate professors or higher, and they were selected using a stratified random selection method. In this research, data was gathered by

means of a questionnaire. Percentages, correlations, t-tests, & two-way analysis of variance were used to examine data. (ANOVA). The results of the experiment supported the theory that university faculty in South Western Nigeria who also work part-time have lower student outcomes than their counterparts who do not.

Mohd Zdikri bin Md Sabron et al (2018) The purpose of this research is to investigate how workers feel about their coworkers' side gigs. This research is a causative study, which means that its purpose is to identify the main variables that are linked to workers engaging in moonlighting. Conceptually, this research builds on Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory. Further, both fundamental statistical methods and more sophisticated analysis methods were employed to assess results. Factor analysis, correlational regression analysis, & Hayes model method for mediator impact were all used in this research. Findings indicated a favorable and statistically significant connection between workers' participation in moonlighting and both external and psychological factors. The findings highlight the interplay between individual and contextual variables that drive workers to take on side gigs. Workers' attitudes toward illumination are more important than their own conduct. The investigation ended with a statement and some suggestions for future research.

Marco Fugazza et al (2016) created a versatile model with 2 types of work: the traditional paid (tradable) sector, where employees may include those without contracts and who are having trouble getting them, and the traditional unpaid (non-tradable) self-employment sector. Key model factors such as relative wage bands/self-employed revenue, relative wage bands/self-employed sector growth, & real exchange rate are shown to exhibit distinct trends as a result of the interplay between shock categories & institutional settings. Empirical evidence suggests that extra compensated casual subsector plays a significant part in propagation of trade disruptions. Trade deregulation has been linked to a decline in self-employment, but the rise of irregular production necessitates the addition of this factor.

Okpalaibekwe et al (2022) Third-level government, or local government, was established to enable community growth & resource mobilization. Sadly, Anambra State's local government has not been able to fulfill its constitutionally required duties. As a result, some people began to query whether or not local governments actually exist as a distinct tier of state governance, as studies showed that they often fell short of expectations in terms of service delivery & consequences this had for local government growth. The study's overarching goal is to evaluate how effective career management is in boosting output in the local government sector in Anambra State. The study looked into how career development and planning affected workers' performance in Anambra State Local Government Councils, how career mentoring influenced workers' motivation to do better, and how career counseling affected workers' dedication to achievement of councils' organizational goals.

Alessandra Guariglia et al (2006) Moonlighting trends of the working-age people in Russia are analyzed using data from Russian Longitudinal Monitoring Survey (RLMS). Results showed that moonlighting is short-lived and that previous job-hopping aspirations are correlated with current moonlighting and prospective job-hopping behavior. In addition, 26.5% of all newly formed businesses were started by people who had already worked for themselves in the past. These findings indicate that working a second job in Russia could be seen as a good way to start up new companies and contribute to economy in long run.

Davide Taibi Not all Scrum techniques can be used by development teams in moonlighting devs spending no more than 10 hours every week that do not conflict. In this piece, they introduced Moonlighting Scrum, a variant of Scrum designed to maximize productivity by reducing meetings and increasing time spent on actual work. The team set out to do this by adapting Scrum methods in order to strike a balance between their time spent on development as well as communication.

Husain (2014) moonlighting as "working another job in addition to one's main job," whether it be part-time or full-time. (p.6). It's unclear whether this position will be related to the previous one. Depending on the circumstances, it could be either short- or long-term. (Sangwan, 2014). The term "moonlighting" is used here to describe an academic who teaches at multiple institutions at once. In this article, the term "professor" will be used to describe any individual who is employed full-time in a teaching capacity at designated Christian institution, regardless of their level of education.

It has been theorized that moonlighting can be explained by a number of different models. **Betts (2006)** divides them up into two groups: monetary and behavioral. Moonlighting is primarily seen as a revenue generator in economic theories. Dispositional theories recognize that there's more to motivation for moonlighting than money. Theory of scarcity was the first dispositional paradigm. It's commonly believed that people who rely on the moon economy are

poor and socially isolated. Aspiration theory is the second dispositional paradigm. Moonlighters are seen as unique individuals who have greater drive and ambition. As opposed to scarcity theory, this perspective is more optimistic. Betts contends it was more successful than scarcity theory in gaining adherents.

Wisniewski and Hilty (as cited in Raffel & Groff, 1990) Recommends 3 suggestions for why teachers might take on extra work: to supplement their income, to pursue personal interests, and to prepare for a future career change. Teachers are more likely to take on extra work if they are also the primary earner in their household, according to research by Raffel and Groff (1990). (p.410). Financial & diversionary or growth variables were discovered to be the most important causes of moonlighting.

Economists may find the solution to the problems of the labor market in the percentage of workers who also work part-time. In reality, according to **Allen (1998)**, working two jobs is a logical response to underemployment in first. A individual may search for a second employment to make up for hours they aren't able to devote to their first, basic job.

Amuedo-Dorantes and Kimmel (2009) argue that in times of high unemployment, poor pay, & anticipation of a "future economic downturn," employees must take on additional jobs to ensure financial security for their families.

Heineck and Schwarze (2004) moonlighting because of money worries, to gain relevant work experience, because they enjoy it, or because they fear losing their current employment.

Husain (2014) provides 2 main justifications: financial limitations & pursuit of a favored work range. Job diversification may be pursued for a variety of reasons, including but not limited to: reducing exposure to a single employer's risks; gaining experience in a variety of fields; hedging against financial setbacks by working multiple jobs at once; or replacing a wife's labor force participation with that of her husband.

Sangwan (2014) provides an overview of the advantages, including financial, time spent working, skills gained, professional paths explored, employment stability, & need to start one's own business.

Nunoo, Darfor, Koomson, and Arthur (2016) the relationship between employees' willingness to take on extra labor and the stability of their jobs in Ghana. They discovered that individuals who have one steady work are less likely to freelance if they have greater job stability. However, they discovered that individuals with multiple occupations were more likely to engage in moonlighting.

In the United States, Amuedo-Dorantes and Kimmel (2009) found that (1) Blacks moonlight more than Whites; (2) married men, men with a greater responsibility for their families, men and women in more wealthy regions moonlight compared to single men, men with fewer children, or men residing in poorer states; (3) those with higher levels of education appear to be less likely to moonlight; and (4) those with higher levels of income and employment in the private sector were linked to less moonlighting. Long-term workers in low-skill industries, for instance, were more apt to pick up extra shifts. Allen's (1998) study of the motivations of the single found that: (1) young single women had more reason to moonlight to save for the future than older single women; (2) women searched for an additional job to meet family responsibilities than men did; and (3) having a large extended family decreased the likelihood of moonlighting. All these studies' results demonstrate that individuals are pushed into moonlighting by fiscal and social considerations.

Raffel and Groff (1990) claim that working a second job is not inherently unethical or harmful, and that there should be further investigation into studies that paint a bad picture of teachers who do so. (p. 404). However, they say that having an additional work has the greatest impact on their family and social life, followed by their ability to read and study independently, their bodily health, and their moral or emotional well-being. Overworked employees and poor health, rivalry, business confidentiality in a risk of conflict of interest, ineffectiveness because of dealing with multiple jobs, as well as a moral quandary while working for two employers from same company are just a few of issues that moonlighting can cause, according to Sangwan (2014). The favorable aspects of moonlighting include increased job movement (the likelihood of obtaining a new position), access to a robust network due to increased interaction with more people, enhanced skill set, and decreased employee attrition. (Sangwan, 2014).

KaukabAra and Aisha Akbar (2016), The author of A Study of the Impact of Moonlighting Practices on the Job contentment of University Teachers tests the hypotheses that moonlighting has an effect on job contentment, as well as whether this effect can be traced back to factors such as salary, professional development opportunities, and

student evaluations. There was a negative correlation between work happiness and factors such as salary, education level, opportunities for advancement, and overall evaluation, as found in the research.

A Shaji, George & A.S Hovan George (3j July 2022): - The report that has been based on how moonlighting affects the IT sector. The report that states that the moonlighting has been done by the employees for the additional income, now a days the employees in India earn less income comparing to other nations. This makes people work in different firms. As we concluded that this can't be controlled, the only way to deal with this is if the second job affects the productivity of the employee and the firm proves it then the necessary actions must be taken against them. And rules must be made with the interest of both parties.

DR. Hardeep Kaur & MS. Kavita Saini 2020: - The majority of employers don't have any problem with employees doing the moonlighting. In other hand there are employers who don't promote this behavior the main reason is the business privacy, competitive threat and productivity issues. Instead of irradiating the moonlighting the managers can handle it smoothly by specifying the rules and regulations of the company regarding the moonlighting. The HR department does have an important part in managing people and the workplace.

Kakub Ara & Aisha Akbar (Jun. 2016): - The topic was actually how moonlighting affects employee productivity. The study states that there's substantial influence in job satisfaction, also the income is one of the major parts. The company which states the promotion plans and all the employees are extremely satisfied. The workload has been increased and it is stated by the employees. The main reason behind the moonlighting is the basic pay. Human resources play a crucial role in recruiting, hiring practices tenure and salary.

Vikas Choudary & Garima Saini (Jan 2020): - Organizational dedication was found to serve as a complete mediator between work happiness and side gigging in this investigation.. During the pandemic the number of employees started doing a lot of jobs, in order to earn more money. The organization can't ban moonlighting, the organization must consider the valuable recommendation and also creating rules and policies for the moonlighting will help.

IV. RESEARCH GAP

Moonlighting is a scenario which has not been invented recently but discovered. It has been ever present since long for all who wants to earn a little more. Recently it has been more prominently noticed in the tech industry and has become a topic of debate among companies, where some are strictly against it and calling it a cheating on part of the employee while some others support it as far as the employee productivity remains the same. Our research will help understand the effects of moonlighting and the novelty is we'll find out if actually efficiency or productivity is affected by comparing moonlighting employees with non-moonlighting employees.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Methodology in research is the "how" of a study. It is the method by which a researcher effectively prepares a study in order to ensure valid and dependable results that tackle study's focal points and objectives. The section on methods addresses two main concerns: Which methods might be used to collect or generate the data? In what manner will it be investigated?

Articles, journals, research or review papers, and online sources have all been used to assemble secondary data. This essay examined a number of issues surrounding side jobs in the workplace.

Research Design: Research Design is a plan for a study, it is used for collecting, measuring, and analyzing the data. Research design is a blueprint or framework for How to collect the data? How do measure the data? How do analyze the data?

Proposed Research Design: The observational research method is being used for this investigation. Descriptive study aims to gather information about a phenomenon, situation, or community in order to describe it in detail. In this case, it is more helpful in answering "what," "when," "where," & "how" queries than "why" query posed by study challenge. As a result, we can assess the impact of extra work on an employee's output.

Target Audience: Prior to conducting any studies, it is necessary to settle on and commit to a specific target audience. The term "target population" is used to describe the total group or populace that the scholar intends to study. After that, a selection frame is built based on the intended group.

Secondary data were utilized for this chapter.

VI. CASE STUDY

Judge Ozaki's Case

Moonlighting at the International Criminal Court?

The destiny of Judge Ozaki's tenure at International Criminal Court was discussed and decided by seventeen of the Court's eighteen justices on March 19, 2019. In January of this year, Judge Ozaki submitted a proposal to Presidency to transition from "full-time judge" to "non-full-time judge" of the Court. The stipulation was acceded to. A few months later, in February, Judge Ozaki notified Court that she had been named envoy to Estonia for Japan, with her new position set to begin on April 3, 2019. She is currently an envoy, but she asked to maintain her role as a "non-full-time judge" in case of *The Prosecutor v. Bosco Ntaganda*.

The Decision

The court decided that justice Ozaki could fulfill his obligations under Article 40 of the Rome Statute while serving as a "non-full-time judge" as defined by Article 35(3). The Statute guarantees judicial impartiality in Article 40, which goes as follows: 1. The judicial branch shall operate without interference from any other branch of government. 2. Judges are forbidden from taking part in any actions that could compromise public trust in the legal system or their own impartiality. In addition to their judicial duties, judges who are obliged to reside at the court's main location may not hold any other work positions. Fourth, the justices must reach a unanimous decision on any issue concerning the interpretation of clauses two and three. If the issue at hand involves a specific court, then that judge will recuse themselves from the decision-making process. The vast majority of people agreed that provisions of this piece constituted "concrete" criteria. Furthermore, court decided that requirement pertaining to "professional nature" under clause (3) did not apply in this instance because Judge Ozaki's position was discontinued "full-time" after her request. The Rome Statute's Article 40 was distinguished from the International Court of Justice's Article 16 clause. (ICJ). No member of Court may participate in any governmental or managerial role or other employment of a professional type, as stated in the latter provision. Clauses (1) & (2) of Article 40 of Rome Statute, in comparison, are broad in scope. The majority of the panel concluded that this was the case because the authors of Rome Statute had omitted crucial factors on purpose.

The Court's interpretation of the standards as "case-to-case" emphasized the importance of the "actual occupation" at issue. The meaning of "is likely to" in the under phrase was a central part of the majority decision. To the majority, word meant "a level of certainty outside of merely conjecture or possibilities," which seems to be an independent meaning. As a result, the majority concluded that Judge Ozaki's role as Japan's envoy to Estonia did not interfere with her role as a judge in Ntaganda's case because neither Estonia nor Japan were involved in the matter. It's obvious that the majority relied on a skewed understanding of the criteria laid out in Article 40 of Rome Statute. The majority could have given the issue more thought, but the view is not wrong. Contrarily, "the perception of independence of the judiciary in the view of rational outside observers," was the central focus of the minority opinion, which the majority had ignored. The minority opinion seemed to be aware that Judge Ozaki's continuation would give the accused a chance to file a motion for expulsion or possibly a ground for appeal, both of which could damage public confidence in the Court if the judge were to perform a managerial or political operate for a state party. This apprehension is understandable, as similar petitions have previously been filed with international criminal courts, typically with the express purpose of postponing the prosecution.

Concluding Remarks

The current case is not the first time that moonlighting has been a problem for the International Criminal Court. During the Celebici trial, ICTY was in a comparable position. Judge Odio Benito was chosen as Vice-President of Republic of Costa Rica, so all four defendants in that case submitted a petition to have her removed from case on grounds that she was not an impartial judge as needed by international law. Since Costa Rica was a non-permanent member of Security Council at the time, careful review of issue was necessary. Judge Benito's potential to sway Security Council deliberations over ICTY and the situation in ex-Yugoslavia follows. However, the agency took notice of Judge Benito's promise not to assume the role of Vice President until she had completed her legal obligations. After reviewing her credentials, the agency concluded that she did not need to recuse herself from proceedings at hand. We discover no discussion of 'popular trust in the impartiality of the judiciary' in either of these

instances. Though such concerns might seem inconsequential in the case of an ad hoc body, they are of crucial importance to the International Criminal Court, which relies heavily on the cooperation of its state participants.

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has mentioned the "appearance of judicial independence" on several occasions. The ECtHR's proposed two-pronged test, which takes into account both subjective factors on bias and empirical evaluation of the "appearance of bias," is reflected in ICTY case law. It was shocking to see that most people were ignoring this obvious consideration. It is similarly puzzling that the Code of Judicial Ethics is not mentioned at all. Perhaps this can be attributed to the long-standing custom of giving justices a great deal of deference. Nevertheless, at a time when the Court is experiencing a credibility crisis, when state parties are not reluctant to leave the court, undermining public trust in the system will only furnish more reasons for the state parties to abandon the court. The lack of options available to foreign tribunals in such cases is regrettable. To give one specific example, it is noteworthy that justice Ozaki "threatened to resign" from her position as a justice on the Court if her request was not given in the current case, as put forth by Kevin Jon Heller. Since Article 74(1) of Rome Statute requires all justices to be present at all phases of the hearing, the Court would have to retry the Ntaganda' case from the beginning if her motion was refused. It is therefore easy to conclude that majority didn't have many options and therefore opted for a quick and dirty solution. Furthermore, if we're going considering a general situation, bringing a new judge in the middle of a complicated criminal prosecution could be troublesome and definitely counter-productive. Although 'self-regulation' has been advocated by some, it has not proven effective in other international tribunals. Fortunately, the ICJ has lately demonstrated a path forward in light of all these worries. The announcement that its justices would not "normally agree taking part in international arbitration" last year was a huge move in this direction.

As well as raising serious concerns about their independence and neutrality, ICJ's judges have been criticized for their widespread involvement in international litigation. The Court's willingness to take action to resolve the issue is commendable. Which being said, ICC's taking a comparable tack wouldn't be a bad idea. We shouldn't get our expectations up, though, because justices are suing the Supreme Court for a salary increase. In a court meant to close "impunity gaps" caused by faulty local justice systems, judge impartiality is crucial. For these reasons, the Court should move to prevent this kind of behavior. One possible strategy for doing so could be to only ever comply with such demands in extremely rare cases.

VII. CONCLUSION

Despite moonlighting might not be a significant threat to some businesses, some employees may choose to work a second job in order to supplement their income if they are paid poorly at their primary jobs as well as cannot otherwise afford to do so. While many companies and businesses have policies that forbid their workers from holding more than one job and penalize those who do, others don't mind if their workers take on extra gigs, especially if they're only working there temporarily.

It has been noted that number of moonlighting instances has increased as it has become simpler for workers to work on a second job or company without their main employer's awareness, despite the fact that epidemic has contributed to a culture of working from home for majority of population. In the year 2020, thousands of people lost their jobs as a result of the economic slowdown brought on by COVID-19 and the subsequent shutdown. As a result, many people who work from home have taken on side gigs to supplement their primary revenue, with some estimates putting the figure as high as 70%. Employee performance suffers, data and private information are at risk, & employee might be breaking the law by working a second employment.

Tools and methods were created by many businesses to monitor for and stop moonlighting dangers like data leaks and daylighting. These methods generate a daily red flags report describing workers who may be engaging in moonlighting or displaying other signs of data leaks or intellectual property misuse. Companies should have a distinct policy on moonlighting outlined in employee handbook, the information technology policy, & job contract.

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